

STUDY ON IN-SITU SYNTHESIZED TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

Near-alpha based heat resistant titanium matrix composite reinforced with multi-dimensional reinforcements were synthesized by common casting and hot-forging technologies. Tensile properties at room and high temperatures, and creep behaviors were tested. Mechanical properties of composites were significantly enhanced by the reinforcements.

Keywords: Mechanical properties; in situ; titanium matrix composites, TiB

1. Introduction

High temperature titanium alloys serve as the structural materials for aero-applications because of their low density, high strength, high modulus, corrosion resistance and so on. However, applications of titanium alloys in aero-industry are strongly limited by the temperature, most of the titanium alloys can only serve at the temperatures up to 600°C. For higher serving temperature of the titanium alloys, some alloying elements and ceramic reinforcements are added to improve the mechanical properties.

Among the discontinuous reinforcements chosen in TMCs, TiB is considered the best due to its high strength, high thermal stability and similar thermal expansion coefficient to titanium [1-5]. Rare earth elements are proved to be useful, which effectively improve the mechanical properties and thermal stability of high temperature alloys [6]. Moreover, hybrid reinforced composites can be in-situ synthesized via reaction between titanium and various compounds easily. Systems like Ti-B₄C, Ti-ReB₆ (Re stands for rare earth element) and Ti-B₄C-ReB₆ have been widely studied, and the properties of the hybrid reinforced composites show considerable advantages over the singly reinforced ones [7-10].

In the present study, TMCs based on a near-alpha high temperature titanium alloy are in-situ synthesized by common casting and hot-forging technologies. Mechanical properties of the matrix alloy and TMCs are tested. The effects of reinforcements are investigated in particular.

2. Experimental procedure

In synthesizing titanium matrix composites, the raw materials are grade I sponge titanium, B₄C powder (>99%), LaB₆ powder (>99%) and alloying materials for synthesizing matrix Ti-Al-Sn-Zr-Nb-Mo-Si alloy such as AlMo (50%Mo), TiSn (65%Sn), AlNb (50%Nb), Zr, Al, and Si. Stoichiometric amounts of sponge titanium, B₄C, LaB₆, and alloying elements are blended and melt in a consumable vacuum arc-remelting furnace. The ingots are melted twice in order to ensure the chemical homogeneity. For TMC1, no B₄C is added and only the reaction “12Ti + 2LaB₆ + 3[O] = 12TiB + La₂O₃” takes place. And for TMC4 no LaB₆ is added and only the reaction “5Ti + B₄C = 4TiB + TiC” takes place. The theoretical volume fractions of TMCs are listed in Table 1. After casting, the ingots are hot-forged at 1100°C, rolled in a triple-roller mill at 1000°C in succession. The final rods are about 15mm in diameter. The alpha-beta transformation temperatures of the matrix alloy and TMCs are different, as shown in Table 1. The annealing temperatures for the materials are 20°C higher than the alpha-beta transformation temperatures.

Table 1. Theoretical volume fractions and transformation temperatures of the materials.

Specimen	Volume fraction (%)			Alpha-beta transformation temperature
	TiB	TiC	La ₂ O ₃	
Matrix alloy	/	/	/	1030°C
TMC1 (2.4%)	1.82	/	0.58	1045°C
TMC2 (5%)	4	0.42	0.58	1090°C
TMC3 (10%)	8.16	1.26	0.58	1110°C
TMC4 (10%)	8.29	1.71	/	1080°C

Samples for optical microscopy are directly cut from the rods. Then the samples are prepared using conventional techniques of grinding, polishing and etching. Tensile are along the working direction. Cylindrical specimens for the tests are 5mm in diameter and 30mm in gauge length. Tensile tests are carried out on Japanese SHIMADZU materials testing machine at room temperature, 600, 650 and 700°C. Tensile creep tests are conducted on CSS-3905 testing machine at 600, 650 and 700°C. Temperature fluctuations of tensile and creep rupture tests at high temperatures are controlled within ±0.2°C. Under each testing condition with a given temperature and strain rate, three specimens are tested. JSM-6700F scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is used for examining the microstructure of the specimens. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) foils are prepared by argon ion milling. The foils are examined in JEM-200CX electron microscopes operated at 200kV.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructural characterization

Figures 1 [10] show the microscopy of the matrix alloy and TMCs along the forging direction. The matrix alloy exhibits a near fully laminar microstructure. The matrix microstructures of TMCs are refined by the reinforcements. Laminar spacing is 0.5~3µm for the matrix alloy and TMCs. According to previous studies [2-3, 5],

whiskers are TiB and the particles are TiC. The TiB whiskers are observed with a good alignment along the forging direction.

Figure 1. Optical microscopy of the matrix alloy and TMCs along the forging direction: (a) TMC1, (b) TMC2, (c) TMC3, (d) TMC4 and (e) Matrix alloy.

3.2 Tensile properties

Room temperature tensile properties of the matrix alloy and TMCs are listed in Table 2. Room temperature tensile properties of the materials are not sensitive to strain rates. In comparison with the matrix alloy, tensile strengths of TMCs are significantly enhanced. The tri-reinforced TMC3 with the highest volume fraction of reinforcements is enhanced most greatly. Ductility of TMC1 is also enhanced.

Table 2. Room temperature tensile properties of the matrix alloy and TMCs.

Specimen	Ultimate strength (MPa)	Fracture strain (%)
Matrix alloy	1060	11.0
TMC1	1130	13.0
TMC2	1200	8.2
TMC3	1300	4.2
TMC4	1250	3.2

High temperature tensile properties of the matrix alloy and TMCs are listed in Table 3. TMC1 with the lowest volume fraction of reinforcements shows the best tensile properties at all temperatures except 600°C. And the dependence of strength enhancement on volume fraction is completely reverse to that at room temperature. At 873K, TMC2 with the medium volume fraction of reinforcements shows the highest strength.

Table 3. High temperature tensile properties of the matrix alloy and TMCs.

Strain rate and specimen	Ultimate strength (MPa)			Fracture strain (%)		
	600°C	650°C	700°C	600°C	650°C	700°C
Matrix alloy	790	620	500	18	23	30
TMC1	870	820	755	21	27	36
TMC2	950	810	670	15	19	26
TMC3	900	730	620	11	16	20
TMC4	860	715	600	8	11	15

3.3 Enhancement mechanism of tensile properties

SEM images of TMCs near the fracture surfaces after room temperature tensile tests are shown in Figure 2 [11]. Most TiB whiskers in TMCs are fractured. Figure 3 [10] shows the SEM images of TMCs near the fracture surfaces after high temperature tensile tests. It can be found that the fracture mechanism of TMCs at high temperatures is quite different from that at room temperature. Interfacial debonding is frequently observed in most TMCs at high temperatures. On the other hand, most of the TiB whiskers in TMC1 still fracture (Figure 3(a)).

Figure 2. SEM images of TMCs near fracture surfaces after room temperature tensile tests: (a) TMC1, (b) TMC2, (c) TMC3, (d) TMC4.

Figure 3. SEM images of the tensile specimens along the load sections near the fracture surfaces: (a) TMC1 at 700°C, (b) TMC2 at 650°C, (c) TMC2 at 700°C, (d) TMC3 at 650°C.

At room temperature, TiB whiskers can carry the stress from the matrix effectively, which can be confirmed in Figure 2. So the enhancement is mainly dependent on the volume fractions of reinforcements. Fracture mechanism changes at high temperatures. Interfacial debonding cause stress concentration and strongly reduces the strengthening effect, so the dependence of strength enhancement on volume fraction is completely reverse to that at room temperature. Since the TiB whiskers in TMC1 are mostly slim (with high aspect ratios), which is effective for carrying the load in the matrix. And the fracture mechanisms of TMC1 are similar for room temperature and high temperatures.

3.4 Steady state creep rates

Steady state creep rates of the matrix alloy and TMC1 are shown in Figure 4 [12]. Creep resistance of the matrix alloy is quite similar with IMI834. In comparison with the matrix alloy, the creep resistance of TMC is significantly enhanced by the reinforcements at any temperature or stress. The apparent stress exponents of the matrix alloy at different temperature are around 4.5. The apparent stress exponents of TMC1 are relatively high.

Figure 4 Logarithmic stress dependence of logarithmic steady state creep rates for the matrix alloy and TMCs at different temperatures

3.5 Enhancement mechanism of creep resistance

As reported by the references, the enhancement mechanism of the creep resistance of metal matrix composite can be summarized as two factors: threshold stresses and stress transfer effects [13].

A simple method can be introduced to determine the threshold stresses [14]:

Creep data of TMC1 are plotted as $\dot{\epsilon}_c^{1/4.5}$ versus σ on double linear scales. Good linear relationships prove that the true stress exponents of TMC1 are also 4.5 in the low and high stress regions respectively. Threshold stresses are the abscissae of crossing points between the lines and the stress axis (x-axis) in Figure 5. The stress dependence of TMC1 and the matrix alloy at 600, 650 and 700°C can be written as

follows (units of $\dot{\epsilon}$ and σ are s^{-1} and MPa respectively):

$$\begin{cases} 873K : \dot{\epsilon}_c = 6.0932 \times 10^{-19} (\sigma - 38)^{4.5}, \dot{\epsilon}_m = 7.2139 \times 10^{-19} \sigma^{4.5} \\ 923K : \dot{\epsilon}_c = 5.3166 \times 10^{-18} (\sigma - 20)^{4.5}, \dot{\epsilon}_m = 1.1993 \times 10^{-17} \sigma^{4.5} \\ 973K : \dot{\epsilon}_c = 5.8879 \times 10^{-17} (\sigma - 13)^{4.5}, \dot{\epsilon}_m = 2.5288 \times 10^{-16} \sigma^{4.5} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5 Creep data compensation of TMC1 with threshold stresses

Even after the compensation of threshold stresses, the steady state creep rates of TMCs are still lower than the matrix alloy. So threshold stresses can not fully explain the creep resistance enhancement [15-17]. A coefficient β can be introduced to express the effect of stress transfer at an effective constant stress ($\sigma - \sigma_{th}$):

$$(1 - \beta)^n = \frac{\epsilon_c}{\epsilon_m} \quad (2)$$

where n is the true stress exponent, and β is the stress transfer coefficient from the matrix to the reinforcements ($0 \leq \beta < 1$). For the matrix alloy, β is zero.

According to Formulae (1) and (2), the values of β at different temperatures are listed in Table 4. It is noted that stress transfer effects increase with the rising temperature. Considering the threshold stresses, it can be found that the enhancement of creep resistance is mainly attributed to threshold stresses at lower temperatures and stress transfer effects at higher temperatures respectively

In the composite, internal stresses in the matrix are transferred to the stiffer TiB whisker, and the modulus of the matrix and TiB whisker (E_m and E_w respectively) determine the proportion of transferred stresses. Since 600, 650 and 700°C are inside the $0.4 \sim 0.6T_m$ range (T_m stands for the melting point of titanium), E_m decreases as temperature rises. Due to the high melting point of TiB, E_w changes little. When temperature is higher, the contribution of the TiB whiskers is higher too. So β shows a monotone increasing relationship with temperature.

Table 4. Influence of temperature on the stress transfer coefficient β in TMC1

Temperature	600°C	650°C	700°C
β	0.037	0.165	0.277

4. Conclusions

In the present study, hybrid reinforced high temperature titanium matrix composites (TMCs) are *in-situ* synthesized by common casting and hot working technologies. Mechanical properties of TMCs are significantly enhanced by the reinforcements. It can be concluded as follows:

(1) At room temperature the enhancement of strength is mainly dependent on the volume fraction of reinforcements, while the high temperature strength shows a different enhancement mechanism, which is mainly dependent on the interfacial debonding between the TiB whiskers and matrix.

(2) High apparent stress exponents of TMC1 are successfully explained by threshold stress. Enhancement of creep resistance in TMC1 is mainly attributed to threshold stresses at lower temperatures and stress transfer effects at higher temperatures respectively.

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